

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AMONG STUDENTS - FUTURE TRANSLATORS USING A TEACHING THESAURUS

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ABSTRACT

Since the purpose of education is now correlated with the formation knowledge of key competencies, a modern understanding of the training of a hundred is built on the basis of the formation of students' professional tendencies. The competence-based approach assumes that the student does not master specific forms of knowledge and skills, and mastering them in a complex. Concerning the system of teaching methods is changing, more precisely; the system of teaching methods is defined differently. At the core selection and design of teaching methods lies the structure of the corresponding general competencies and the functions they perform in education. The following article is devoted to the formation of professional competence among students - future translators using a teaching thesaurus.

INTRODUCTION

When forming the professional competence of a translator of professionally oriented texts, even before the start of training, it is necessary to understand what set of competencies he should have at the end of the training. During research on special technology were designed key and subject competencies, and OTAP was a necessary means of learning in the formation of professional competencies of a translator. Yes, by graduation from the university, the student-translator must be prepared for solving certain problems. As specified in the "Requirements for professional training Specialist" in the specialty "Translation and Translation Studies", graduate- the translator must have:

- a high level of development of theoretical thinking,
- ability to correlate the conceptual apparatus of the studied disciplines with real facts and phenomena of professional activity, the ability to creatively use theoretical provisions to solve practical professional tasks;
- be able to use scientific, reference, methodological literature on native and foreign languages;
- master the methods of information retrieval.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As previously mentioned, the problem of the professional competence of a translator has been repeatedly addressed in translation studies, but so far there is no consensus in translation studies about

translation competence and its components, and in relation to the activities of a translator of professionally oriented texts, this issue is practically not considered by researchers to this day. Considering all of the above, we want to highlight the main, in our opinion, professional translation competencies of a translator of professionally oriented texts:

- Linguistic competence - knowledge of at least two languages - one's own and a foreign one, knowledge of language means, norms and rules.

- sociocultural competence or "background knowledge" - includes knowledge of "national cultural characteristics of the social and speech behavior of native speakers: their customs, etiquette, social stereotypes, history and culture, as well as ways to use this knowledge in the communication process".

- the technical competence of a translator includes the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to perform translation activities. First of all, it is knowledge about translation strategies, translation techniques and transformations.

- information and technological competence - by this concept we mean the possession of computer technologies, information search on the Internet, possession of electronic dictionaries and catalogs, as well as any search for information using any information media and work in different search engines.

In the formation of metalinguistic competence, a system of methods: research, heuristic, problem presentation, reproduction, information-receptive method. The above classification of methods were implemented in the work through a system of exercises. Mandatory characteristics of the system of exercises

for the formation of professional competencies with the help of OTAP are scientific and communicative the orientation of the entire system, the interdependence of exercises, their accessibility, consistency and repeatability of language material and speech actions.

So, the system of exercises for the formation of a professional potential with the help of OTAP, as revealed in the course of the study, should be comply with the list of the following requirements:

- focus on achieving ultimate goals;
- rational sequence of exercises;
- the principle of gradation of difficulty;
- the relationship between classroom and home exercises, thanks to which all preparation for future professional activity becomes a goal;

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Translation studies as a linguistic science is characterized by the ambiguity of terminology. Therefore, the metalanguage of translation studies is a rather complex entity, which can be understood and comprehended when referring to a logically closed subset of the scientific thesaurus at the level of the academic discipline "Translation Theory", designed for students to assimilate it in order to successfully navigate and function in it. The model representation of the meta-units of English translation studies is a network that takes into account the relationships between concepts and the lexical units that implement them (hierarchical relationships - hyperonymic; non-hierarchical - relationships of antonym, synonymy, variability, correlation).

CONCLUSION

At the same time, the process of forming the student's thesaurus in the subject area

under consideration represents his training in its entirety. In addition, the teaching thesaurus on English translation studies with its semantic graphs for topics and subtopics by discipline is an effective didactic tool designed to organize

independent work of students in preparation for classes in translation theory, to independently determine the trajectory of learning and in writing term papers and dissertations in translation studies.

References:

1. Klimzo B.N. Craft of a technical translator. On the English language, translation and translators of scientific and technical literature. 3rd ed., corrected and supplemented - M.: "R. Valent", 2011. - 488 p. Latyshev L. K.,
2. Provorotov V. I. The structure and content of the training of translators in a language university: Educational and methodological manual. - 2nd ed., stereotype. — M.: NVI-TEZAURUS, 2001. — 136 p.
3. SmekaeV V.P. Modern technical translation. Tutorial. English language. — M.: Valent, 2014. — 360 p.
4. Cheburashkin N. D. Technical translation at school. Textbook of technical translation for students of grades IX–X. schools teaching a number of subjects in English. [Ed. B. E. Belitsky]. Ed. 2nd, dorab. M., "Enlightenment", 1976. - 319 p.
5. Karasik V.I. Transformation of knowledge in the modern era: linguistic and cultural aspect // Izvestia of the Volgograd State Pedagogical University. 2017. No. 3 (116). pp. 88-94.
6. Khaleeva I. I. Fundamentals of the theory of teaching the understanding of foreign speech (training of translators): author. dis.. Dr. ped. Sciences: 13.00.02 / I.I. Khaleev. M., 1990. 32 p.
7. Khamidovna N. S. On The Use of Infinitive Groups in German and Uzbek Languages //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 202-204.
8. Sofiboyeva PhD G. M. DEVELOPING PUPILS' LOGICAL THINKING ABILITY IN THE STUDY OF GEOMETRIC MATERIALS IN MATHEMATICS OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS //Central Asian Journal of Education. – 2021. – T. 6. – №. 1. – C. 1-9.
9. Sofiboyeva G. DEVELOPING IMAGINATION ABOUT SPACE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE LEARNING PROCESS //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2021. – C. 4-8.
10. Nazikhovna G. Y. PROGRAMMING AND ROBOTICS BASED IN STEAM LEARNING //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – T. 2. – C. 58-87.
11. Yunusova G. N. THE PROGRAM FRONT PAGE-PROGRAM OF MAKING WEB PAGE AND E-BOOK //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 230-233
12. Kosimov, A. (2022, February). THE ROLE OF CRITICAL READING STRATEGIES ON READING COMPREHENSION IN EFL STUDENTS AND ITS IMPACT TO SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. In International journal of conference series on education and social sciences (Online) (Vol. 2, No. 2).
13. Kosimov, A. A. (2021). The importance of needs analysis in teaching and enhancing english language proficiency among uzbek efl learners. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 11(11), 616-623.

14. Игамбердиева, Ш. (2021). Развитие навыков творческого сотрудничества будущих преподавателей иностранного языка при использовании технологии «бит-урок». Общество и инновации, 2(11/S), 190-198.
15. Игамбердиева, Ш. А. (2019). АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПРОБЛЕМ УСВОЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ УРОВНЯ В1+. Мирская наука, (12), 174-178.
16. Галимуллина, Л. (2021). Некоторые особенности в переводе фразеологических единиц с английского языка на узбекский язык. Общество и инновации, 2(8/S), 205-213.
17. Шокирова, М., & Абдуллаева, Н. (2021). Стилистический анализ в процессе преподавания английского языка. Общество и инновации, 2(6/S), 110-116.